

CONFERENCE ABSTRACT

Parents and kids. How children got sixth disease and fifth disease in lockdown at the time of SARS-CoV-2 pandemic

Laura Mazzoleni*, & Stefano Mazzoleni

Specialist Medical Student, Postgraduate Course for General Practitioners, Autonomous Province of Bolzano, Italy

Sixth disease (Exanthem subitum) and Fifth disease (Erythema infectiosum) are two infectious diseases very common in infancy; parents generally believe that their children get infected from peers sharing the same spaces (e.g. kindergarten companions or siblings). From March to May 2020 in Italy exceptional measures were taken to contain the new Corona virus SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. These measures strongly reduced or cancelled contacts between children; nevertheless, in that period we registered 13 cases of sixth disease and 3 cases of fifth disease in a single paediatrics' office. These children stayed always home and had contacts only with their parents or close relatives; seven of them were only son; adults had only occasionally contacts with the outside using personal protective equipment. Lockdown has been not only a necessary measure to contain the SARS-CoV-2 spread but also an unprecedented biological experiment that shed new light on old infectious diseases. Our experience confirms that asymptomatic adults often transmit sixth and Fifth diseases to their children and can help people to be aware of transmission mode of these infections.

Keywords: Sixth disease, Fifth disease, SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, Lockdown, Pandemic, carriers

**Presenting Author*

Graduated in "Medicine and Surgery" in 2019 at the University of Padova, I had the opportunity to deepen my knowledge on the subject while spending one year abroad at the University of Munster, in Germany. Being active as an educator at the scout group "AGESCI" for two years has helped me to develop my natural aptitude in human relations, an important skill I made use of while working as a front office secretary at a General Practitioner's clinic during my University studies. Pursuing my studies in "General Medicine" I currently work as a General Practitioner's registrar in Bolzano and as a Doctor in a "USCA", an emergency medical service for Covid patients, since October 2020 in Merano.
